

Interlinked Computing: Initial Forecasts

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Our project explores the future of interlinked computing: how connections, networks and grids between many independent, separately owned, systems, will work together. We are looking to establish relevant trends in software, see how those trends may develop in the next fifteen or so years towards 2040, and to deduce some implications for the future.

Based on nine interviews with expert futurists as the first step in a Delphi study, we offer these possible forecasts for comments. They are in the form of statements, both predictions, and concerns needing research now.

1 Predictions

This section offers a range of predictions about the future of connected systems.

1.1 Artificial Intelligence

In 2040, Generative AI will permit practical contextual generation by non-experts of virtually any text, image, video, and code.

By 2040, AI has developed exponentially, with AI success prompting funding and development; and with AI itself generating improvements in its own programming and context.

By 2040, Competition between owners of AI technology—both multinational companies, and the superpowers USA and China—have both fired exponential development of AI, and motivated 'short cuts', widespread AI deployment without considering consequences.

In 2040, Quantum processing is only just beginning to be widely used in AI algorithms.

In 2040, The 'everyone can code' will lead to the disaggregation of systems, allowing, for example, a mass of tiny, single-person, clothing and similar brands to replace the current large brands.

In 2040, AI bots are increasingly replacing humans behind text-based interfaces, both representing individuals and companies; AI systems will also negotiate between themselves for processing resources.

In 2040, Political decisions about AI will follow the pattern of random public focus on specific aspects leading to legislation about those aspects only.

In 2040, The major players in 'big technology' will deploy significant political power and therefore regulatory capture.

In 2040, Cultural differences, such as different attitudes toward privacy in the US, China and Europe, have led to different usage of AI.

1.2 Ubiquitous Connectivity

In 2040, continuous, always-on, high-bandwidth connectivity will be the expectation, available almost everywhere.

In 2040, sensors and actuators (such as motors) will be practical and the norm.

In 2040, the 'edge processing' power associated the distributed sensors, devices and communications infrastructure will complement centralised 'cloud processing'.

1.3 Personal Sensors and Mixed Reality

In 2040, personal devices have much increased processing power and sensor capacity, allowing them to maintain continuous context to support their owners, and authentication based on continuous tracking of the individual.

In 2040, adoption of fully-immersive artificial reality will be a minority activity.

In 2040, it will be commonplace for people to spend up to 10 hours daily in a mixed reality environment, especially in industrial contexts.

In 2040, individuals will control their physical assets such as home energy systems using 'digital twins' in this mixed reality 'metaverse'.

In 2040, this resulting 'collision' of the physical and virtual roles will use ultra-fast 'embarrassingly parallel' processing.

1.4 Digital Ownership

In 2040, tokenisation will provide ownership of public web assets—such as rights to virtual advertising in specific real-world spaces—to be validated and traded.

In 2040, a variety of new local forms of 'money' will be traded.

2 Possible Problems

This section proposes some issues that we expect to become serious problems.

2.1 Problems Directly Related to AI

In 2040, it is difficult to distinguish truth from fiction due to the ubiquity of AI and its accessibility. AI is a threat to objective truth and verification.

In 2040, AI driven cyber-attacks have led to a malware and anti-malware arms race.

In 2040, the democratisation of AI has caused a democratisation of skills and a loss of workers in all professional roles.

In 2040, AI has facilitated the creation of malicious code that looks legitimate and benign.

In 2040, the use of AI for social conditioning and social manipulation is commonplace.

In 2040, many systems are beyond human understanding.

By 2040, a megadeath accident will have happened due to AI-controlled systems.

In 2040, dangerous ideologies have been formed about AI.

In 2040, the AI arms race (between both states and big tech) has led to corners being cut in the development of safe AI.

2.2 General and Social Systems

In 2040, the ubiquity of sensors has facilitated environments which can not only authenticate you but also identify you.

In 2040, there is an inability to distinguish accidents from incidents due to the decentralised nature and complexity of systems.

In 2040, the digital divide will be widened resulting in rising inequality.

In 2040, excluded groups such as the elderly and unskilled workers have become targets for populist politics.

In 2040, there are more accidents and catastrophic failure modes due to the complexity of systems.

In 2040, the localisation of digital currencies presents new socio-political and economic challenges.

In 2040, governance and regulation have become very difficult because everything is fragmented.

By 2040, Energy use by computing has increased enormously because of the higher demands of AI.

3 Possible solutions:

The interview discussions identified many ways to address some of these problems. Here are some possibilities:

- Creating 'ambient accountability' where there is no code to allow misbehaving bots. Or there is real-time governance.
- Legislation around AI safety and the establishment of government AI purchasing safety principles.
- Workers displaced by automation being retrained in other areas.
- New degree courses combining technical skills and regulation.
- Expertise from social sciences and anthropology engaged to fully understand the complexity of the emerging technological landscape.
- The establishment of a holistic organisation looking specifically at global data interchange.
- AI finding ways to reduce AI's energy use.
- Building data centres close to clean energy sources (data is easier to transport than energy).